

Positional Accuracy Provided by State-of-the-Art Cooperative Awareness and Collective Perception

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Abstract—Cooperative awareness (CA) and collective perception (CP) deal with the exchange of perception data within vehicle-to-everything (V2X). The achievable and needed accuracy is not yet analyzed in detail. The baseline for accuracy is the data from simulations, recommendations provided by standards, or various perception datasets with a disconnect between localization accuracy and perception accuracy. We extended a state-of-the-art (SOTA) automated driving (AD) platform with CA/CP functionality in our work. We then deployed it on two street-legal AD demonstrators (ADDs) and did an extensive field test to acquire data. With the data, we show the achievable accuracy of SOTA systems and discuss the requirements for future implementations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) is the communication link within an intelligent transport system (ITS). V2X allows an automated vehicle to get information without detecting the information with classic onboard sensors, such as a camera, lidar, or radar. The information can be as simple as active speed limits or traffic jam warnings. It can also be more complex information, such as CA data, sent directly from an ITS station (ITS-S) to inform everyone about its location. Most recent standards define CP information, meaning sharing onboard perception information. ([1])

The integration of CA and CP information depends on the received information's accuracy. The accuracy of CA messages (CAMs) [2] and CP messages (CPMs) [1] can be encoded into the respective message as confidence parameters. The car2car communication consortium (C2C-CC) also specifies basic system profile requirements [3] that regulate the minimum accuracy, such as *RS_BSP_209*, which states 5 – 15m positional accuracy, depending on driving conditions. However, specifications do not determine the accuracy needed by complete systems. Related Research, such as Miller et al. [4], provides an analysis of the root-mean-squared (RMS) error for a system that shares the global navigation satellite system (GNSS) data and compensates for the time delay of the transmission. Others, such as Li et al. [5], created an algorithm that selects the objects to send via CPM, depending on if the information improves the CP. Finally, several system implementations are worth mentioning, as they show how CP works in field environments [6]–[8] and simulations [9]–[11].

However, the above-mentioned implementations do not discuss details of the achieved and possible accuracy of the

data. To be specific, there is a lack of comparing the accuracy provided by components of V2X in relation to the onboard perception in a fully implemented AD stack. Comparing CA/CP information with the onboard perception will provide a baseline for discussions of needed accuracy. Furthermore, this allows for discussing accuracy requirements on transmission delay compensation and global fusion implementation in future contributions. Hence, in our work, we equipped two street-legal ADDs with V2X to share CA and CP information. We compare the positional information provided by the onboard perception of the ego vehicle with the CA/CP data from the second vehicle. This analysis provides insight into the accuracy of single elements of CA/CP.

This paper will start by shaping the problem domain in Section II, followed by the description of scenarios in Section III. Next, the measurement setup is presented in Section IV, followed by the actual measurements and their results in Section V and VI. Findings on the accuracy of CA/CP will then be discussed in Section VII, followed by a discussion on related research in Section VIII. Finally, this paper concludes the findings of this work in Section IX.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Within CP, object data is transmitted between ITS-Ss. The accuracy of the object data depends on three factors: (i) the accuracy of the localization, which is the reference position of the sensor data of the sending ITS-S, but also the reference position of the receiving ITS-S, (ii) the accuracy of the sensor, which is caused by insufficient intrinsic and extrinsic calibration, as well as the used object detection model, and (iii) the time accuracy, which is caused by the time delay of sensor data.

In this paper, we discuss the end-to-end accuracy between two vehicles. For this, we compare the CA and CP information from one vehicle with the onboard perception of a second vehicle within three consecutive scenarios, as described in Section III. We use the perception of the first vehicle as a reference, as the AD stack is calibrated to the onboard perception. In other words, an automated vehicle is designed to deal with minor accuracy deviations of onboard perception, as will be discussed in Section VII.

The end-to-end accuracy can be visualized with three specific questions. These questions will be discussed in Section VII to provide a basis for future implementations and standardization:

- 1) How accurate is SOTA CA/CP?
- 2) How accurate does it have to be?

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- 3) How do the standardized requirements compare to SOTA system requirements?

III. SCENARIOS

For this paper, we defined three scenarios, shown in Figure 1. Each scenario includes parameters causing a deviation in accuracy, as described below. We performed each scenario twice. Once at a standstill and once with moving vehicles. On top of that, we performed each test in a different location to mitigate the potential for biases and errors caused by testing in a single location.

Scenario I aims to reveal details of the localization of vehicles, i.e., the reference position for CAMs and CPMs. Hence, Scenario 1, shown in Figure 1, has two vehicles. One vehicle is broadcasting its position via CAM. The ego vehicle detects this other vehicle with its onboard sensors. The positional difference between onboard sensors and CAMs is the accuracy of CA.

Scenario II aims to reveal the accuracy of CP. The simplest form is the inverse of scenario 1, as shown in Figure 1. The scenario has a car that sends out CPMs, containing the position of the ego vehicle. The ego vehicle knows its position. The positional difference between the localization of the ego vehicle and the position received via CPM is the accuracy of CP.

Scenario III aims to reveal the accuracy of a full CP scenario. The scenario shown in Figure 1 has two vehicles detecting a pedestrian. The ego vehicle uses its perception to detect the pedestrian and receives an additional CPM from the other vehicle. By comparing the positional difference between the local perception and the CPM, we get the full accuracy of CP.

A. Locations

The scenarios are carried out at three locations, shown in Figure 2 to mitigate potential biases toward localization with lidar HD maps. Additionally, the distances between vehicles at these locations fall into the accuracy categories defined by the lidar precision discussed in Section IV-D.

$< 10m$ is a parking space on the Graz University of Technology campus, as shown in Figure 2. The vehicles were parked facing the same center point and $\sim 7.5m$ apart, with $\sim 83.5^\circ$ angle, to allow optimal detection by the object detection algorithm. This setup is below $30m$ and, therefore, the best setup for the accuracy of the lidar. It is also the best setup for the highest amount of possible lidar points to ensure optimal detection of the size of the other vehicle.

$30 - 60m$ is an intersection on the Graz University of Technology campus, as shown in Figure 2. Compared to the previous scenario, one vehicle was turned $\sim 180^\circ$ to extend the tested parameters. The vehicles were parked $36m$ apart, with $\sim 94.5^\circ$ angle. This setup is in the medium accuracy range of the lidar.

$> 60m$ is a side street on the Graz University of Technology campus, as shown in Figure 2. Compared to previous scenarios, the vehicles were parked directly facing each other, with only a small angular offset allowing correct

vehicle detection. The vehicles were parked $\sim 62m$ apart, with $\sim 189.0^\circ$ angle. This setup is in the upper accuracy range of the lidar.

B. Dynamic Scenarios

Dynamic scenarios start like the static scenarios, as described in Section III-A and as shown in Figure 2. One of the vehicles starts driving in a straight line over the crossing center. The other vehicle follows as soon as the center point is crossed. The first vehicle stops when it reaches the same distance to the center point. The other vehicle does the same. Hence there is always one vehicle driving, overlapping both of them driving. Also, the setup of the scenarios does not allow to dynamically move the pedestrian, as the driving paths of the vehicles block a controlled route for the pedestrian.

IV. SETUP

The measurement setup consists of two street legal ADDs of the Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH¹. The following Sections will provide detail on the vehicle hardware setup in Section IV-A, followed by a description of the used AD software stack in Section IV-B and details of the V2X communication platform in Section IV-C. Finally, Section IV-D to IV-F will provide additional technical details necessary for the discussion.

A. Automated Driving Demonstrators

Both vehicles have hardware and software components that allow street-legal AD in Austria. The computing hardware for both vehicles is three-year-old mid-range consumer hardware, as shown in Table I.

TABLE I
HARDWARE SETUP — ADDS

Type	Ford Fusion	Ford Mondeo
CPU	Intel i7-9700K	Intel i7-11800H
GPU	Nvidia RTX 2070	Nvidia RTX 3070 Mobile/Max-Q
RAM	32GB DDR4	32GB DDR4

The Ford Fusion, shown in Figure 3, is equipped with four lidars, an Ouster OS2-128 and three Ouster OS1-64, as well as two cameras, both of which are FLIR Blackfly S. Typically, the lidar point clouds are fused, and the result is fed into the object detection. The camera data is then used for labeling detected objects. However, for this work, we use the single OS2-128 lidar for object detection to have a minimal test set without the multi-sensor setup as overhead. The processing software for this setup will be discussed in Section IV-B.

The Ford Mondeo, also shown in Figure 3, has a dynamic sensor platform and is equipped with sensors, depending on the use case. This work uses a single Ouster OS2-128 lidar to detect objects. The processing of information is similar to the software within the Ford Fusion, as discussed in Section IV-B.

¹<https://www.v2c2.at/automated-driving/>

Fig. 1. Scenario 1 (left): the ego vehicle (red) detects the other vehicle (gray) with its onboard sensors. The other vehicle broadcasts its location via CAM. — Scenario 2 (middle): the ego vehicle (red) receives its position from the other vehicle (gray). — Scenario 3 (right): the ego vehicle (red) detects a pedestrian and receives the position of the pedestrian from the other vehicle (gray) via CPM.

Fig. 2. Measurement locations 10m, 30m, and 60m (l.r.). Satellite perspective (top) with vehicle and pedestrian positions. Third-person perspective (bottom) with highlighted vehicles (arrow) and pedestrian positions (circle).

Fig. 3. The Ford Fusion (left) and the Ford Mondeo (right), each equipped with an Ouster OS2-128 (circle).

B. Autoware Universe

Our ADDs adopted the Autoware Universe² software stack and extended it with CA/CP capability. The perception pipeline, shown in Figure 4, is essential to this work. The primary source for object detection is the lidar sensor. The lidar sensors' raw data is pre-processed and distributed to the localization and perception modules. The output of the localization module, discussed in Section IV-E is used by the predict-plan-act system and the V2X gateway components.

²<https://www.autoware.org/>

The localization provides the geo-referenced position of objects for CPMs and the ego-vehicle position for CAMs.

In parallel, the sensor data is used for object detection. After a pre-processing stage, including filtering techniques such as ground-plane-removal and a compare-map-filter, the output is fed into a CNN for 3D object detection. In the final step, called shape fitting, the shape of the detected object is refined.

At this point, we must mention two different configurations of the perception pipeline for the Ford Fusion and the Ford Mondeo. The Ford Fusion uses a downsampled point cloud to reduce CPU load during processing for older hardware. This slightly reduces accuracy. However, the perception pipeline of the Ford Fusion introduces object validation techniques to remove obvious false positives. Tracked objects are fed back to the shape fitting to deal with under-segmentation and over-segmentation. This process results in an optimized shape-fitting, improving the result. In general, different configurations like these influence the accuracy of the perception, as discussed in Section VII.

The detected objects are now fed into the local tracking algorithm. At this point, the process is similar to the localization before. The data is distributed to the predict-plan-act

system for vehicle control and to the V2X gateway, which creates the CPMs. The CA/CP data sent is received by the other vehicle with the V2X gateway. The CAMs and CPMs are converted to object data, similar to the local data. This data is then fed into the global tracking. Finally, the global tracking fuses the locally tracked data with the CA/CP data received via V2X. The current implementation relays the CAM and CPM data to the predict-plan-act system. The fusion and its challenges are a topic of future work.

C. V2X Platform

The vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox is a collection of hardware and software components to allow easy access to V2X communication. Details of its features and the setup can be found in the respective free and open source software (FOSS) repositories on GitHub [12]. For this work, we use a Raspberry Pi 4 8GB as a computing platform and an Unex SOM301-E as a V2X communication module. The routing core for managing communication modules is running on the Raspberry Pi. The performance of the vehicleCAPTAIN hardware is discussed in parallel works with pending publication, and will be linked on GitHub [12]. Figure 5 shows the interaction between vehicleCAPTAIN software components. Put simply, a V2X message is received by an Unex SOM301-E, processed with the Unex API, and put into a ZeroMQ stream by the routing core. The ZeroMQ message is then relayed via ethernet to the V2X Gateway, which converts the ZeroMQ-packed V2X payload into a ROS2 Autoware message. Sending works exactly in the opposite direction.

D. Details: Lidar Precision

Both vehicles use the Ouster OS2-128 for localization and object detection. Hence, the accuracy of localization and object detection is shaped by the accuracy of the lidar sensor. The datasheet [13] specifies a resolution of $0.3cm$ and an accuracy of $2.5-8cm$ depending on the distance. The angular accuracy is 0.01° vertically and horizontally.

E. Details: Localization

Both vehicles use a lidar HD map for localization. This allows each vehicle to localize with a precision of $2.5cm$ according to the lidar precision mentioned in Section IV-D. The localization uses the normal distributions transform monte-carlo localization (NDT-MCL) algorithm provided by Saarinen et al. [14]. This algorithm allows highly accurate yet fast localization. The lidar HD map has a global navigation satellite system (GNSS) point as a reference. As the same lidar HD map is used in both vehicles, the GNSS reference point is the same; hence we can mitigate the inaccuracy of GNSS. For the validity of results, we, therefore, add two discussion points: (i) the localization via HD maps is SOTA in many implementations, as it allows much better localization in urban environments, where big buildings block access to GNSS sources, and (ii) the inaccuracy added by GNSS can easily be added, as discussed in Section VII.

F. Details: Reference Time

For the dynamic scenarios discussed in Section III, we synchronized the clocks of our ADDs via chrony and local NTP servers. This results in time variations of up to $5-6ms$. The resulting delay will always be part of the CP accuracy. However, this is below 10% compared to the $10Hz$ cycle time of the perception.

V. MEASUREMENTS

The measurements are conducted for three static and dynamic scenarios at three different locations. This aims to validate the system at different distances and across different localization points in the lidar map, as discussed in Section III. In Section IV-E, we showed that the vehicles use the same HD map for localization, hence having the same GNSS reference for localization. This mitigates GNSS inaccuracies during measurements.

The static measurements were recorded for around $5min$ each for a solid statistical baseline. The dynamic measurements of scenario I-III are recorded as long as the scenario takes with $\sim 5km/h$, which is around $1-2min$, depending on the distance. The CAM/CPM sending frequency is $10Hz$ each.

The measurement results are described as Root Mean Squared Errors (RMSEs). The RMSE of the distance d_{RMSE} is calculated as shown in Equation 1. The input parameters are the Cartesian coordinates of the locally perceived (lp) object and the Cartesian coordinates of an object perceived via V2X.

$$d_{RMSE} = \sqrt{(x_{lp} - x_{v2x})^2 + (y_{lp} - y_{v2x})^2} \quad (1)$$

The RMSE of the rotation Ψ_{RMSE} is calculated as shown in Equation 2. With the input parameter yaw (ψ) of the lp object and the V2X object, respectively.

$$\Psi_{RMSE} = \sqrt{(\psi_{lp} - \psi_{v2x})^2} \quad (2)$$

Finally, one must also compare the perception data in the same time frame. Hence we used the *Approximate-TimeSynchronizer*³ to match an object received via V2X with the same object in the local perception. This tool allows matching messages depending on timestamps. For this work, the offset is $100ms$ maximum to compare the objects at their respective time of creation, without interpolation.

VI. RESULTS

The first data set is the bounding boxes of the perceived vehicle and the pedestrian, as shown in Figure 6. In other words, we analyzed scenarios I and III and compared the perceived object size in meters with the ground truth. The ground truth of vehicle sizes is from the respective datasheets. The ground truth of the pedestrian is estimated as $0.3/0.5m$ width/height.

The second data set is the RMSE of the distances in meters and the rotation in radians. The graphs in Figure 7 are

³https://github.com/ros2/message_filters/blob/rolling/index.rst

Fig. 4. The logical data flow in the Autware Universe assisted V2X implementation, running on the ADDs.

Fig. 5. The processing flow for receiving messages in the vehicleCAPTAIN stack: an ITS-G5 message is received and processed by the Unex hardware and software. The routing core handles the relaying to the vehicle stack via Ethernet. The V2X gateway processes the respective incoming message for the Autware environment. Sending works exactly in the opposite direction.

ordered row-wise to scenarios I-III. In each case, we used time stamp matching, as discussed in Section V, and allowed $\pm 100ms$ of time deviation in the filter, which allows $10Hz$ cycle compensation of the maximum CPM frequency.

As one can see, the evaluations do not contain results for dynamic measurements with pedestrians in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The setup of the scenarios did not allow us to also dynamically move the pedestrian, as discussed in Section III.

VII. DISCUSSION

Figure 8 shows the local and global perception in the RVIZ debug viewer. One can see the ego vehicle and its local and global perception. This section will discuss the detected object sizes in Section VII-A, the actual RMSEs in Section VII-B before discussing the initially stated questions from Section II in Section VII-C.

A. Detected Object Sizes

One can see in the graphs shown in Figure 6 that distance is, of course, a factor. The more lidar detection points available, the more accurate the bounding boxes are. However, one can also see in comparison to the scenarios shown in Figure 1 that the object's rotation is important to determine its depth/length. The Ford Fusion and Ford Mondeo had issues determining the exact length of the other vehicle when there was a too-straight angle, as seen in locations *E* and *F*.

Regarding pedestrians, one can see the issues with bounding boxes in general. Pedestrians are overestimated because crossed arms in front of the body or a relaxed stance influence how many lidar points hit the target pedestrian. Pedestrians who are farther away get hit by fewer lidar

points. Hence they are slimmer. This can also be seen in the mid-range transition scenarios where the pedestrian size has a much higher standard deviation.

In conclusion, the bounding box is fitting for general approximations of an AD system to know whether an object is there. However, underestimating the bounding box generates an offset for the center of the bounding box, which is a major part of the inaccuracy within CP, as discussed next.

B. RMSE Evaluation

The most critical parameter is the RMSE of the distances. It provides the general positional accuracy of our system. As discussed in Section IV-E, the localization only depends on the lidar accuracy, as the same HD map is used for localization. This results in around $2.5cm$ localization accuracy, as discussed in Section IV-E. If GNSS is used for localization, one can add GNSS localization inaccuracy to the RMSE.

With the setup given in this work, scenario I, shown in Figure 7, compares the onboard perception with the localization of the other vehicle. Hence the results are inaccuracies produced by the local perception, two times the localization, and time delay, which leads to two effects. First, static measurements are more accurate than their dynamic counterparts, partly caused by the $< 100ms$ time offset and partly by the tracking algorithm of the object detection reacting on movement. Second, the RMSE is higher if the distance gets bigger. This issue relates to the bounding box size issue discussed above.

Scenario II compares the onboard localization with CPMs describing the ego position. As with scenario I, the accuracy error is again the combination of the perception accuracy, two times localization, and the time delay. The similarity is shown by comparing the d_{RMSE} in Figure 7.

In terms of rotation, scenarios I and II also have similar performance. As one can see, the absolute values are way off, but the standard deviation is small. This is due to the 180° rotation effect discussed in Section VII-A. In the $30m$ location, we deliberately parked one vehicle with the back side towards the center, as shown in Figure 2. Yet, object detection decided its the front.

In scenario III, the distance is less of a problem for pedestrians, as they are comparatively small and nearly cylindrical objects. Hence, bounding box errors create no big

Fig. 6. Results of detected vehicle sizes $[m]$ in scenario I (top) and pedestrian sizes in scenario III (bottom). The x-axis shows static measurements (A, C, E) and dynamic measurements (B, D, F), each with distances (10m, 30m, 60m).

Fig. 7. Results of the RMSEs for distances $[m]$ and rotation $[rad]$ in scenarios I-III (t.b.). The x-axis shows static measurements (A, C, E) and dynamic measurements (B, D, F), each with distances (10m, 30m, 60m).

Fig. 8. The local and global perception from the ego vehicle (slightly opaque vehicle). The local perception (blue) is overlaid with CAMs (orange) and CPMs (green).

offsets. However, the rotation is difficult to estimate if the person is not walking forward.

C. Accuracy of CA/CP

Using lidar localization, one can see that CA/CP systems with SOTA AD stacks do not compromise accuracy in static scenarios. The performance of CA/CP depends strongly on the distance caused by the distance-dependent density of the lidar point cloud and the connected object detection algorithm that has to fit the bounding box depending on the point cloud data. In numbers, at 10m and standstill, one can expect 0.2 – 0.3m RMSE on average, with a standard deviation of 0.01m. In dynamic scenarios with 60m distances, the RMSE is between 0.88 – 1.73m on average and 0.49 – 1.04m standard deviation. The lower RMSE is of the Ford Fusion, with the optimized perception discussed in Section IV-B.

For the rotation, one can expect $2.3 - 2.5^\circ$ RMSE with a standard deviation of $0.07 - 0.7^\circ$ when the object's angle is visible. The rotation strongly depends on how the vehicle's surface is perceived. Warped fronts of vehicles also influence the perceived rotation. Despite these issues, the rotation can be wrong 180° , and the rotation of pedestrians is impossible to detect with the used CNN without movement.

The results show that CA/CP predominantly depends on the perception system and strongly depends on localization. The AD stack of Autoware works best with $< 0.1m$ accuracy for lateral localization and, depending on the driving speed, between $0.1 - 10.0m$ longitudinal localization. Object detection is in similar ranges, depending on the use case. A CA/CP system has to work in lower ranges if the data should be used as direct input, as the localization of the receiving vehicle is added to the accuracy. However, if the information is just used to inform other vehicles of the potential presence of objects, i.e., a vehicle approaching an intersection, the importance of accuracy may be discussed.

Finally, one can discuss the standardization specifications of V2X messages. As initially mentioned, the C2C-CC specifies $5 - 15m$ localization accuracy, which is insufficient for exact positioning use cases when dealing with pedestrians in parking spaces at low speeds. However, the specifications may not yet include the newest CA/CP integration approaches, with the CPM standard planned to be released in 2023.

VIII. ADDITIONAL RELATED RESEARCH

The works in this paper focus on the current standard of CPMs. However, related research also deals with issues strongly connected to the applicability of CA/CP. Issues that influence accuracy, methods that can improve accuracy, and methods that use CA/CP in other ways that need accuracy. The following paragraphs provide an overview.

The discussion about dynamic scenarios in Section VII indicated that delay influences the accuracy of information if it is not compensated. The sending frequency is related to delay and, therefore, the mechanisms to prevent congestion [15]–[20]. The accuracy of a single message is the same, independent of congestion control. However, more messages allow the AD stack to increase detection accuracy. The more information the fusion algorithms have, the more precise the result.

The validity of the data also influences the accuracy. In other words, when malicious data is received, it will corrupt the overall perception accuracy. Related research deals with cyber security threats [21]–[24], and methods to guarantee the trustworthiness of data [25]–[28].

Technologies under development may increase the accuracy of CP. This work uses 802.11p for data exchange, which is a cmWave protocol. Related research deals with mmWave protocols [29]–[31], which have a much broader bandwidth and allow sharing of raw data. Overall, as stated in previous research [32], the accuracy can be increased; however, with the results in this paper, the necessary effort may be discussed.

This work discussed the mitigation of GNSS accuracy by using lidar HD maps. If one aims to achieve similar results by using GNSS for localization, one has to improve the accuracy. This can be done with real-time kinematic (RTK) data or by cooperative methods [33], [34].

IX. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we discussed the accuracy performance of a CA/CP system. The system is based on Autoware Universe, a SOTA AD stack that we extended with the V2X communication capability of the vehicleCAPTAIN toolbox [12]. The resulting CA/CP software stack was deployed on two street-legal ADDs to be tested for three scenarios at three locations. The result is a dataset describing the offset between local and global perception with RMSEs of the distance and rotation as their results. We can show that the biggest errors are caused by bounding box errors in object detection. We also hint that the localization with GNSS instead of lidar localization will decrease accuracy. Finally, we discussed our results with the accuracy specifications demanded by AD stacks and accuracy demands provided by the C2C-CC.

In parallel works — already accepted, but not yet published — we discuss the delay behavior of CA/CP systems. As discussed in Section VIII, the delay behavior and the overall accuracy are strongly connected. A major challenge is integrating delayed CA/CP data into the active perception. Hence, in future works, we will fuse the global CA/CP data and aim to provide further insight into the applicability of CA/CP in street-legal automated vehicles. Especially the integration of V2N data could be interesting, because of the advantage of a higher packet delivery rate. Similarly, we aim to discuss data cleanliness and trustworthiness, which can corrupt the resulting fused perception system.

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